

Comparison On Taste, Brand And Purchase Decision Between Teh Botol Sosro And Ichi Ocha

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Viciwati, Vania Utamie Subiakto ⁽²⁾Ranny Nuryapraja (43115010309)
Faculty of Economics and Business, Faculty of Communication, Mercu Buana Jakarta University

Abstract

The objective of the study is to identify the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of taste, brand and purchase decision. Within the conduct of the study, the number of the samples that had been involved was 120 respondents and the data analysis technique that had been implemented was the one-sampled t-test and the Mann Whitney test. Based on the results of the study, it might be concluded that there is not any difference between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of taste, brand and purchase decision. Therefore, in the future both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha should focus more on improving the product quality and also the overall quality. In addition, both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha should pursue good business communication in order to stay on the top of the brands.

Keyword: Business Communication, Product Quality, Taste, Brand, Purchase Decision

1. INTRODUCTION

A number of products have been present in Indonesia and the presence of these products has been a new phenomenon that consumers always enjoy. Within the globalization era nowadays, the community experiences a number of changes in multiple life aspects; the ease of information exchange in the globalization era has led to the modernization of the community, both the one in the city and the one in the village. Such change has also impacted the rapid development of the food and beverage industry; as a result, the companies within this industry should have accurate business strategies. In relation to the statement, Kotler argues that consumers will select the products that offer quality, performance or innovation. A product will not gain success if it is not supported by appropriate price, distribution, advertisement and sale (Kotler & Killer, 2015).

Various food and beverages have become the peculiar identity of every people since they like hunting and tasting numerous phenomenal and peculiar food and beverages. One example of such a case is that nowadays people prefer tea as their complimentary beverage whenever they have their meal. However, due to the long processing activities, serving tea has been rare especially for the community of the Capitol. The limited time due to the busy schedule has been the main reason why the community in the Capitol rarely serve tea. As an alternative, people in this kind of community prefer more practice and ready to serve-tea that will not take much of their time and effort.

As having been explained, all of these situations take place because of the changes in the economy and the life style in the communities of both the cities and the villages. Due to these situations, the consumption pattern in these communities has also changed, including the tea consumption. The changes pattern of consumer consumption toward the more practical beverage has lead to the rapid development of packaged tea. On the other hand, the rapid development of the packaged tea industry is influenced by the presence of the marketing and the branding by each brand of packaged tea such as Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. In relation to the statement, Kotler argues that brand refers to the name, the term, the sign, the symbol, the design or the combination of all elements that have been assigned in order to identify the product or the service by a seller or a group of sellers and their competitors, serves as a strong emotional bond between the consumers and the products and serves as the benchmark for the strategic options and strengths that might influence the financial aspects (Phillip, 2000).

With regard to consumption patterns, the purchase decision might be triggered by product branding activities until the packaging process. Within this cycle, the consumption pattern might increase due to the brand and the impression of the tea package. According to Schiffman & Kanuk (2008:485), purchase decision refers to the selection toward two alternatives or more among the consumers within their purchase. From the previous statements, it is clear that the market segment for the industry of packaged tea or ready to drink (RTD) tea has become more interesting for the companies who would like to launch their new business in Indonesia (Yosi Winosa in Warta Ekonomi.co.id: 2019, accessed in <https://www.wartaekonomi.co.id/read193618/berebut-manisnya-industri-minuman-teh-dalam-kemasan.html>).

The ready to drink tea industry occupies around 5.7% of the total soft drink market segment, which has been predicted about 35 billion litres per year in comparison to dairy drinks (3.1%), juice (3.0%), carbonated drink (2.5%) and isotonic coffee and energy drink (15.7%). These figures have been occupied by the mineral water (galon and packaged mineral water) up to 70%. The implication is that the ready to drink tea becomes the best-selling ready to drink beverage in Indonesia after the mineral water (Yosi Winosa in Warta Ekonomi.co.id: 2019, accessed in <https://www.wartaekonomi.co.id/read193618/berebut-manisnya-industri-minuman-teh-dalam-kemasan.html>).

In the Law Number 18 of 2002, the Government has stipulated the regulations for Food and through the Law the Government has mandated that the Food should be available in sufficient, safe, well-qualified, nutritious and various manner under the affordable price and without any contradiction to the religion, the belief and the culture of the society. By producing well-qualified and safe-to-consume food, it is expected that the community trust will increase and the given food industry will develop so that the annual consumption of several food and beverage product might be increased.

Figure 1. The Sale Figure of Ready to Eat-Foot and Ready to Drink-Beverage

From Figure 1 above, it is clear that the sales figure for food and beverage product has been increasing over the years. In 2015, the sales figure was IDR 1,000 trillion while in 2016 the sales figure was IDR 1,100 trillion. Entering 2017, the sales figure has been IDR 1,200 trillion. The increasing sale figure thus shows that the food and beverage industry in Indonesia has an increasing demand in each year (accessed from <http://www.gapmmi.or.id/>).

According to Kotler & Keller (2013), one of the keys to retaining consumers is consumer satisfaction. Very satisfied customers are usually loyal for a long period of time. They will commit repurchase intention when the company to which they have been loyal introduces new products and updates old products. At the same time, the very satisfied and loyal consumers will discuss the good aspects of the given company and its products with other people and they do not mind the competitors and yet they are not too sensitive-price. In fact, they might share their ideas about the desired product and service to the company and they also enjoy more affordable service costs in comparison to the new consumers due to the number of transactions. All of these aspects might be routines for the company.

The data from the Top Brand Award in 2018 (accessed from <http://www.topbrandaward.com>) with regards to the market share of ready-to-drink tea products and of ready-to-drink green tea products in Indonesia have shown that the ready-to-drink tea products are able to survive in the market competition and have good quality in Indonesia. Apart from the statement, Top Brand is the award that has been rewarded to the best brands selected by the Indonesian consumers.

Table 1. The Data of Ready-To-Drink Tea in 2018

READY-TO-DRINK TEA		
BRAND	TBI	TOP
Teh Pucuk Harum	32.3%	TOP
Teh Botol Sosro	26.8%	TOP
Teh Gelas	9.6%	
Frestea	9.2%	
Ultra Teh Kotak	4.1%	
Nu Green Tea	32.4%	TOP
Frestea Green	20.5%	TOP
Ichi Ocha	20.0%	TOP
Joy Tea	7.7%	

From the data in Table 1 above, with regards to the market share of ready-to-drink tea it is apparent that there are two different brands that have been in intense competition namely Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. Nowadays, the market share of Teh Botol Sosro is 26.6% while the market share of Ichi Ocha is 20.0% and there is a possibility that this figure is increasing since the number of consumer demands has been changing. In order to survive longer within the market competition, both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha should pursue innovation since the packages of ready-to-drink tea products nowadays have been very consumer-friendly. Then, departing from the overall elaboration, the researcher would like to conduct a study that will focus on the purchase decision. The reason is that purchase decision will define which brand that becomes the winner over the market competition. Furthermore, in conducting the study, the researchers will focus on the two brands namely Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. In order to guide the conduct of the study, the researcher would like to propose the following problem formulations:

- What are the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of quality?
- What are the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of taste?
- What are the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of brand?
- What are the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of purchase decisions?

e. How do both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha achieve the ideal sale figure 80%?

Within the conduct of the study, the researchers would like to meet the following objectives:

- a. Identifying the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of quality
- b. Identifying the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of taste
- c. Identifying the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of brand
- d. Identifying the differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of the purchase decision
- e. Identifying how Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha achieve the ideal sale figure 80%

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

In this section, the researchers would like to elaborate on the theories that will serve as the foundations for the conduct of the study. The theories that will be elaborated are Business Communication, Communicative Action, Product Quality, Taste, Brand and Purchase Decision. In addition, the researchers also provide the hypotheses that will be developed for the conduct of the study along with the research framework. The theories along with the hypotheses and the research framework might be consulted in the following sections.

2.1 Business Communication

Business communication is essentially a process of sharing business information and messages in the form of a conducive organizational structure and system for maximizing the effectiveness and the efficiency of the work products. Purwanto (2011:5) states that business communication includes numerous forms of communications, both the verbal ones and the non-verbal ones, with certain objectives that should be achieved. Departing from the statement, there are two forms of communication namely verbal communication and non-verbal communication.

Then, the objective and the function of business communication are strongly associated with an organization. Not to mention, the function of business communication is similar to that of organization communication. According to Sendjaja (in Rosmawati, 2010:101, 102) there are four functions that business communication has in an organization namely:

- a. **Informative:** The informative function is related to the amount of information that organizational leaders and members might need in accomplishing their duties.
- b. **Regulatory:** The regulatory function is related to the facilities for regulating and controlling an organization.
- c. **Persuasive:** The persuasive function is related to the efforts of inviting other people to follow or to execute the given ideas or duties.
- d. **Integrative:** The integrative function is related to the efforts of uniting an overall organization that might consist of several divisions, departments or sections in order that the organization will stay intact and integrated.

Within business communication or marketing communication, there is the brand of the product that will be sold to the community. In this regard, the brand is not just a name or a logo; instead, the brand might be considered as the commitment of an organization (a working unit) to provide its principles toward the consumers. Thus, the brand does offer not only the functional benefits but also the emotional benefits, the self-expression and the social benefits. In other words, the brand does not only keep its commitment but also embarks on a long journey of development based on the perception, the experience, the assessment and the consumer satisfaction toward the given service of the brand (Nastain, 2017:16).

The power of a brand is able to make a tie of loyalty among its consumers and this ability in turn delivers the brand to its success, its endurance and its competitive edge in terms of products. With all of its strengths, a brand might possess different meanings with different objectives. In relation to the statement, MarkPlus Institute of Marketing has identified 6 (six) brand levels (Markplus Institute of Marketing, 2009) namely:

- a. **Attribute**
A brand is expected to remind the consumers toward certain attributes or traits.
- b. **Benefits**
A brand is more than just a set of attributes. The consumers do not purchase attributes; instead, they purchase both functional (durable) and emotional benefits. A good brand does not only possess the power to explain the product to the consumers but also the power to establish consistency over the competitive edge of the product. Thus, it might be implied that the consumers do purchase not only the brand but also the function of the brand.
- c. **Value**
The value of a brand creates the value of a producer. The value that is attached to the product is usually understood by means of a simple manner yet the simple manner represents the overall characteristics of the product. For example, the consumers who use the latest gadget should display themselves as a technology-care person who wants to keep updating their technology and improve their prestige by using the gadget that they have.
- d. **Culture**
A brand represents a certain culture. For example, the brand Mercedes represents the culture of Germany namely being efficient and highly qualified. Then, the brand Honda represents the culture of Japanese, which has been full

of technology and dreams toward the future. The products that have been manufactured in the countries of high culture, high discipline and high quality will certainly be more convincing in comparison to the products that have been manufactured in the countries of low culture and low quality.

e. Personality

A brand should be able to devise a certain personality.

f. User

A brand should leave an impression on its user. This impression might be born out of the experience in using the products of the brand. The high product quality will leave a positive impression and experience for the users and thus will give birth to the loyalty toward the products.

Last but not the least, the conception of a brand itself might serve as an asset that triggers the wave of dramatic change with enormous influence and also an asset that changes the perception of brand marketing and management. This is how actually a brand should be managed and measured and thus it becomes the role that should be played or the responsibility that should be born by the marketing executives (David A> Aker, 2015:3).

2.2 Communicative Action

The Theory of Communicative Action has been derived from the Theory of Communication. Communication is the ultimate requirement for the life of mankind. Without communication, people interaction, specifically the individual, the communal and even the organizational interaction, will never take place. Then, two persons might establish interaction if each person performs action and reaction (Enjang, 2018:19). This action and reaction are performed individually, communally and even organizationally. In addition to the statement, communication might be considered as a process of an activity of delivering messages from one person to another in order to achieve certain objectives (Usodo, 2017:64). As an alternative, it might be stated that communication is the prerequisite for mankind's life.

Returning to the topic, the Theory of Communicative Act is proposed by Jurgens Habermas. Communicative action refers to the action that leads to the rational action in which orientation is an agreement, concordance and mutual understanding. For Habermas, such a situation might only be achieved through rational procedures or a communicative manner by means of intersubjective understanding (Santoso & Wisarja, 2007:241). Habermas highlights people to action, which might be divided into two categories namely the communicative action and the rational-objective action. Then, he divided the rational-objective action into two categories namely strategic action and instrumental action. The strategic action refers to any action which aims at influencing other people to achieve specific objectives. On the other hand, the instrumental action refers to any action which aims at achieving the physical world objectives in order to attain technical efficiency (Watimena, 2007:102).

2.3 Product Quality

The core of the definition of product quality lies in the efforts of fulfilling the customers' needs and desires in order to cope with the consumers' expectations. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2014), product quality refers to the capacity of a product to perform its functions. The functions consist of overall durability, reliability, accuracy, ease of operation and product repairation altogether with the other attributes. Furthermore, Kotler (Mukti, 2015) states that the dimensions of product quality consist of reliability, durability and conformity. Similarly, Tjiptono (1997) states that product quality refers to the quality that deals with the efforts of fulfilling or exceeding consumer expectations. With regards to the statement, the dimensions of product quality that have been developed by Kotler & Armstrong (2006) consist of:

a. Performance

Performance is the most fundamental dimension and is related to the main function of a product. Consumers will be disappointed if their expectation over this dimension is not fulfilled.

b. Reliability

Reliability is related to the profitability or the possibility that a product will successfully execute its function every time the product is consumed in a certain period of time.

c. Feature

The feature might be considered as the secondary aspect because the development of the feature is almost unlimited and goes in accordance with technology development. As a result, the feature becomes the target of the producers for pursuing their innovation in order to satisfy the consumers.

d. Durability

Durability is the dimension that displays the measurement toward the cycle of a product both in terms of period and in terms of technique. A product will be considered durable if the product endures numerous times of consumption.

e. Consistency

Consistency refers to how far a product is able to meet certain standards or specifications.

f. Repairability

Repairability refers to the capacity of being repaired. If a product is broken and it might be easily repaired, then the product will be considered having good repairability.

g. Aesthetic

Aesthetic refers to how a product is viewed, perceived and listened.

h. Perceived Quality

Perceived quality refers to the accuracy of the quality that has been perceived over a product.

2.4 Taste

In order to improve the taste, sometimes additive substance for the beverage is used (Drummond & Breferre, 2010). On the other times, the available beverages do not draw the interest of the consumers although they have high nutrition content. In other words, the quality of a beverage product is defined by the level of the consumer interest toward the product. In general, beverage processing companies always strive to manufacture products with high quality. Beverage quality refers to the overall traits of the beverage that might influence consumer perception. According to Grow & James (2010), the indicators of taste are as follows: scent, taste and oral stimulation. The first indicator might be detected by the sense of smell, while the last two indicators might be detected by the sensory cells in the tongue.

2.5 Brand

According to Tjiptono (2013), brand refers to the sign, symbol, design, colour, movement or the combination of other product attributes that are expected to provide identity and differentiation that discern the product of a brand from the product of a competitor brand. Basically, a brand is also a commitment to consistently deliver a number of certain characteristics, benefits and services from the seller to the purchaser. The brand itself has been used for several objectives and according to Tjiptono (2013) the objectives of using the brand might be related to the name and the symbol within the brand.

2.6 Purchase Decision

According to Buchari Alma (2013), the purchase decision is the decision that the consumers make based on the finance, the technology, the politics, the culture, the product, the price, the promotion, the physical evidence, the people and the process. Consequently, these aspects shape the overall attitude among the consumers in processing all information and making conclusions in the form of a response toward the product that will be purchased. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2004), in general the purchase decision among the consumers are influenced by the following factors:

- a. Need recognition
- b. Information research
- c. Alternative evaluation
- d. Purchase decision
- e. Post-purchase behaviour

2.7 Research Framework

In order to conduct the study, the researchers should design two research frameworks. The research frameworks that have been designed might be consulted in Figure 2 and Figure 3 below.

Figure 2. Research Framework 1

Figure 3. Research Framework 2

2.8 Hypothesis

Based on the theoretical foundation and the research framework that has been elaborated, the researchers would like to propose several hypotheses as follows:

- H₁ : There are differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of product quality.
- H₂ : There are differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of taste.
- H₃ : There are differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of brand.
- H₄ : There are differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of the purchase decision.
- H₅ : There are differences between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of 80%-ideal sale figure achievement.

3. METHODOLOGY

The design that had been implemented within the conduct of the study was the comparative study design. Sugiyono (2014) states that comparative study is a study that compares the situation of one variable or more to the two different samples or more or to the two different times. The researcher implemented the comparative study design in order to identify the comparison between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of product quality, taste, brand and purchase decision.

3.1 Population and Sample

In relation to the previous paragraph, Arikunto (Ridwan, 2013) states that population refers to the overall areas of generalization that consist of subjects or objects with specific quantities of characteristics that a researcher has assigned for the sake of his or her study and verification. The presence of the population in any study is highly important in order to support the description and the discussion of the topic in the study. Then, specific to the context of the study, the population that had been involved was the students of Mercu Buana University Jakarta.

Since the population was too enormous to analyse, the researcher should gather the samples from the given population. According to Sugiyono (2008), in gathering the sample of a population the Isaac and Michael formula might be implemented. The Isaac and Michael formula provides a useful calculation for defining the number of samples based on the degree of error 1%, 5% and 10%. Within the conduct of the study, the degree of error or the sampling error in defining the sample was 5%. By implementing the Isaac and Michael formula (Ideal Value = 24 x 5 = 120), the number of samples that should be gathered from the population was 120 people. Furthermore, in selecting the sample from the population, the researchers implemented the non-probability sampling technique; specifically, the researcher implemented the incidental sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2016), the incidental sampling technique is a sample gathering technique that has been based on incidence; the term incidence implies that the researchers should select anyone that they met as the sample for the study.

3.2 Data Analysis

In analysing the data that had been gathered, the researcher implemented the following method:

a. IBM SPSS Statistics 23 Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive analysis was implemented in order to describe the data statistics such as minimum likelihood, maximum likelihood, mean, sum, standard deviation, variance, range and alike. In addition, the descriptive analysis was implemented in order to measure the data distribution by means of skewness and kurtosis (Priyatno, 2014).

b. Descriptive Study

Within the study, the researchers had already attained that the comparative analysis or the differential analysis. Comparative analysis or differential analysis is an analysis method that has been conducted in order to identify the differences between two variables (data) or more (Syofian Siregar, 2014). The descriptive study itself is one of the studies that aim at providing a complete description of social setting or the studies that aim at exploring and clarifying a social event or phenomenon by describing a number of variables that have been related to the problems or the units under investigation.

c. Data Normality

For the data normality analysis, the researchers implemented the normality test. The normality test aims at testing whether the data that have been gathered are already normally distributed or not. In conducting the data normality test, the researchers implemented the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test under the assumption of normality on the significance value (sig. 2-tailed) > 0.05 and vice versa.

1. Two-Unpaired Sample Mean Differential Test

The two-unpaired sample mean the differential test was conducted in order to identify the presence or the absence of mean differential from the two unpaired groups. In conducting the test, the researchers implemented the Mann-Whitney test, which is part of the non-parametric test. The non-parametric test should be performed when the data that have been gathered are not normally distributed. Since the data in the study were not normally distributed, the Mann-Whitney test should be conducted.

2. One Sample t-test

The approach that had been adopted within the conduct of the study was the qualitative approach. Through the adoption of the qualitative approach, the researchers strive to confirm the research hypotheses by using certain tables in analysing the research data. The tables that had been used were processed by using SPSS 23 for Windows and Excel.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the researchers would like to elaborate on the results of the study further. Then, after elaborating on the results, the researchers would discuss the implications that had been found from the results. Prior to presenting the results and the discussions of the study, the researcher would provide general descriptions of the object of the study first. The complete elaboration on these aspects might be consulted in the following sections.

4.1 General Description

As having been indicated from the beginning of the study, through the study the researchers would like to compare Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of product quality, taste, brand and purchase decision. With regard to the two objects, the researchers would like to provide the general descriptions of both brands.

Teh Botol Sosro was established in 1974 under the name Sinar Sosro Company. Sinar Sosro Company is the first ready-to-drink and bottled tea manufacture company in Indonesia and even in the world. Living after the company, Teh Botol Sosro is one of the prominent brands under Sinar Sosro Indonesia Company and this brand is known for its glass bottle or the RGB (Returnable Glass Bottle). Sinar Sosro Indonesia started from a tea manufacturing company namely Gunung Slamet Company located in Slawi, Central Java.

On the other hand, Ichi Ocha is a brand that has been released under the Indofood Asahi Sukses Beverage (IASB) Company. This company is a joint venture initiative between the Indofood Sukses Makmur Company and the Asahi Group Holdings Southeast Asia Pte Ltd Company from Japan. Ichi Ocha is a ready-to-drink green tea product that has been manufactured by Japanese technology through a "one-time brewing process." Made of the best Japanese green tea leaves, Ichi Ocha offers a special and peculiar taste that has been adjusted to the preference of Indonesian people.

4.2 Results

In this section, the researchers would like to elaborate on the results of several tests that have been performed. These tests are the Normality Test, Descriptive Test and Hypothesis Test. The results of each test might be consulted in the following sections.

4.2.1 Results of Descriptive Test

In conducting the Descriptive Test, the researchers perform a number of tests toward the characteristics of the samples in the study. The characteristics of the respondents that have been tested are Gender, Age Group, Purchase

Decision and Favourite Product. The results of the descriptive test toward the gender of the samples in the study might be consulted in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Respondents' Characteristics Based on Gender

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	MALE	69	57.5	57.5
	FEMALE	52	42.5	42.5
	TOTAL	120	100.0	100.0

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 2 above, 69 subjects (57.50%) are male while 51 subjects (42.50%) are female. Therefore, it might be implied that the consumers of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha are male.

Then, the results of the descriptive test toward the respondents' age might be consulted in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Respondents' Characteristics Based on Age

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	58 – 72 Y.O.	19	15.8	15.8
	38 – 57 Y.O.	25	20.8	20.8
	24 – 37 Y.O.	41	34.2	34.2
	8 – 23 Y.O.	33	29.2	29.2
	TOTAL	120	100,0	100,0

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 3 above, 19 respondents (15.80%) belong to the age group of 58-72 years old while 41 respondents (34.00%) belong to the age group of 24-37 years old. Therefore, it might be concluded that most consumers of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha range between 24 and 37 years old.

Next, the results of the descriptive test toward the purchase decision among the consumers of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 4 and Table 5 below.

Table 4. Respondents' Characteristics Based on Purchase Decision for Teh Botol Sosro

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	2	37	30.8	30.8
	3	44	36.7	36.7
	4	20	16.7	16.7
	5	19	15.8	15.8
	TOTAL	120	100.0	100.0

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 4 above, 44 respondents (36.70%) purchase Teh Botol Sosro for three times in a month and 19 respondents (15.80%) purchase Teh Botol Sosro for five times in a month. This finding implies that most consumers of Teh Botol Sosro purchase the product for three times in a month.

Table 5. Respondents' Characteristics Based on Purchase Decision for Ichi Ocha

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	2	43	35.8	35.8
	3	38	31.7	31.7
	4	22	18.3	18.3
	5	17	14.2	14.2
	TOTAL	120	100.0	100.0

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 5 above, 43 respondents (35.80%) purchase Ichi Ocha for two times in a month and 17 respondents (14.20%) purchase Ichi Ocha for five times in a month. This finding implies that most consumers of Ichi Ocha purchase the product for two times in a month.

Last but not least, the researchers also perform the descriptive test toward the favourite product. The results of the descriptive test for the favourite product might be consulted in Table 6 below.

Table 6. Respondents' Characteristics Based on Favourite Product

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	TEH BOTOL SOSRO	72	60.0	60.0
	ICHI OCHA	48	40.0	40.0
	TOTAL	120	100.0	100.0

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 6, 72 respondents (60.00%) prefer Teh Botol Sosro while 48 respondents (40.00%) prefer Ichi Ocha. This finding implies that Teh Botol Sosro is more preferable among Indonesian consumers than Ichi Ocha. However, both products are still preferable by Indonesian consumers.

4.2.2 Results of Descriptive Statistics Test for Each Variable

In this section, the researchers would like to elaborate on the results of the descriptive statistics test for each variable in the study namely Product Quality, Taste, Brand and Purchase Decision. These variables are tested toward the two brands namely Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. Then, the results of the descriptive statistics test for the Product Quality between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 7 and Table 8 below.

Table 7. Results of the Descriptive Statistic Test for the Product Quality (PQ) of Teh Botol Sosro

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
PQ1	120	1	5	4.43	.857
PQ2	120	3	5	4.16	.648
PQ3	120	1	5	3.96	.965
PQ4	120	2	5	4.14	.813
PQ5	120	1	5	4.22	.812
PQ6	120	2	5	4.22	.747
Valid N (Likewise)	120				

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 7 above, it is apparent that the lowest mean score has been found on the statement PQ3 (3.96) which statement is: “The product is unable to be stored for a long period of time.” The implication of the statement is that the taste of Teh Botol Sosro might change when it is stored outside but the taste might be well-preserved when the product is stored under cool temperature.

Table 8. Results of the Descriptive Statistic Test for the Product Quality (PQ) of Ichi Ocha

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
PQ1	120	2	5	4.34	.815
PQ2	120	2	5	3.85	.837
PQ3	120	1	5	4.08	.909
PQ4	120	2	5	4.05	.858
PQ5	120	2	5	4.16	.889
PQ6	120	1	5	4.06	.823
Valid N (Likewise)	120				

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 8 above, it is apparent that the lowest mean score has been found on the statement PQ2 (3.85) namely: “The product is well-known among the consumers.” The implication of the statement is that Ichi Ocha is already well-known among the consumers although the product is still quite new in the market.

Furthermore, the comparison of the mean score of the Product Quality between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 9 below.

Table 9. Recapitulation on the Mean Score of the Product Quality between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

No	Statements of Product Quality	Mean Score of Teh Botol Sosro	Mean Score of Ichi Ocha
1	The product displays the expected quality.	4.43	4.34
2	The product is well-familiar with the consumers.	4.16	3.85
3	The product is not storage-durable.	3.96	4.08
4	The product meets the consumption standards.	4.14	4.05
5	The product perfectly meets the offered qualities.	4.22	4.16

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by Microsoft Excel (2019)

From the recapitulation in Table 9 above, it is apparent that there have been differences in Product Quality between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. Then, the most prominent difference is found in PQ2; the mean score of PQ2 for both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is indeed the lowest one. The implication of this finding is that there have been different market shares between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha since Teh Botol Sosro has been a long-standing brand in the market competition of ready-to-drink tea while Ichi Ocha has been a new one in the same competition.

Next, the results of the descriptive statistics test for the Taste between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 10 and Table 11 below.

Table 10. Results of the Descriptive Statistics Test for the Taste (T) of Teh Botol Sosro

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
T1	120	2	5	4.57	.632
T2	120	2	5	4.21	.607
T3	120	2	5	4.20	.763
T4	120	2	5	4.20	.763
T5	120	1	5	3.62	1.271
T6	120	3	5	4.33	.690
Valid N (Likewise)	120				

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 10 above, it is apparent that the lowest mean score has been found in the statement T1 (3.62) namely: “The product has various tastes.” The implication of this finding is that the product has a few taste variants.

Table 11. Results of the Descriptive Statistics Test for the Taste (T) of Ichi Ocha

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
T1	120	2	5	4.34	.853
T2	120	2	5	4.08	.784
T3	120	2	5	4.17	.760
T4	120	2	5	4.17	.760
T5	120	1	5	4.11	.818
T6	120	2	5	4.23	.750
Valid N (Likewise)	120				

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 11 above, it is apparent that the lowest mean score has been found in the statement T2 (4.08) namely: “The product does not taste bitter when it is consumed.” The implication of this finding is that the product is well-qualified since it is processed under a one-time brewing system.

Furthermore, the comparison of the mean score of Taste between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 12 below.

Table 12. Recapitulation on the Mean Score of the Taste Between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

No	Statements of Product Quality	Mean Score of Teh Botol Sosro	Mean Score of Ichi Ocha
1	The aroma of the product is special.	4.57	4.34
2	The product has a special taste.	4.21	4.08
3	The product has a special taste that is enjoyable for consumption.	4.20	4.17
4	The product is not bitter when consumed.	4.20	4.17
5	The product offers numerous taste variants.	3.62	4.11
6	The product has a special signature.	4.33	4.23

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by Microsoft Excel (2019)

From the recapitulation in Table 12 above, it is apparent that there have been differences in the Taste between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. Then, the most prominent difference is found in the statement T6. The implication of the most prominent difference is that Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha have different taste and aroma. Not to mention, both brands have different taste variants in each product.

Afterward, the results of the descriptive statistics test for the Brand between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 13 and Table 14 below.

Table 13. Results of the Descriptive Statistics Test for the Brand (B) of Teh Botol Sosro

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
B1	120	2	5	4.51	.674
B2	120	2	5	4.10	.749
B3	120	2	5	4.15	.837
B4	120	2	5	4.08	.856
Valid N (Likewise)	120				

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 13, it is apparent that the lowest mean score has been found in statement B2 (4.10) namely: “The product has good characteristics.” The implication of this finding is that the products of Teh Botol Sosro are poor in terms of characteristics. Therefore, there should further analysis toward the information source, the purchase site, the consumption mean score, the purchase decision and the influence behind the purchase toward the products of Teh Botol Sosro.

Table 14. Results of the Descriptive Statistics for the Brand (B) of Ichi Ocha

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
B1	120	2	5	4.24	.889
B2	120	2	5	4.05	.776
B3	120	2	5	3.98	.912
B4	120	2	5	4.17	.827
Valid N (Likewise)	120				

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 14, it is apparent that the lowest mean score has been found in the statement B3 (3.98) namely: "The product has an easy-to-remember slogan." The implication of this finding is that the slogan that has been used by Ichi Ocha, namely "*Cobain Kesegaran Jepang*" ("Taste the Fresh Tea from Japan") is difficult to remember among the consumers.

As a matter of comparison, the recapitulation on the mean score of Taste between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 15 below.

Table 15. Recapitulation on the Mean Score for the Brand between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

No	Statements of Product Quality	Mean Score of Teh Botol Sosro	Mean Score of Ichi Ocha
1	The brand is well-known among consumers.	4.51	4.24
2	The product has good characteristics.	4.10	4.05
3	The product does not have an easy-to-remember slogan.	4.15	3.98
4	The product has an interesting theme and advertisement.	4.08	4.17

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by Microsoft Excel (2019)

From the recapitulation in Table 15 above, it is apparent that there have been differences in the Brand between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. Then, the most prominent difference is found in the statement B3. The implication of this finding is that the products from both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha have a different slogan and advertisement initiative.

Last but not least, the results of the descriptive statistics test for the Purchase Decision between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 16 and Table 17 below.

Table 16. Results of the Descriptive Statistics Test for the Purchase Decision (PD) of Teh Botol Sosro

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
PD1	120	2	5	4.45	.798
PD2	120	2	5	3.96	.824
PD3	120	2	5	4.19	.759
PD4	120	2	5	4.18	.869
PD5	120	2	5	4.21	.777
PD6	120	2	5	4.20	.846
PD7	120	2	5	4.30	.740
PD8	120	2	5	4.25	.781
PD9	120	1	5	3.97	.957
PD10	120	1	5	3.97	.849
Valid N (Likewise)	120				

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 16 above, it is apparent that the lowest mean score has been found on the statement PD2 (3.96) namely: "I look for information first before I purchase the ready-to-drink tea product." The implication of this finding is that not all consumers are looking for information prior to purchasing the products of Teh Botol Sosro.

Table 17. Results of the Descriptive Statistics Test for the Purchase Decision of Ichi Ocha

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
PD1	120	2	5	4.29	.893
PD2	120	2	5	3.95	.868
PD3	120	2	5	4.03	.783
PD4	120	2	5	3.97	.948
PD5	120	2	5	4.17	.781
PD6	120	1	5	4.06	.853
PD7	120	1	5	4.09	.944
PD8	120	1	5	4.12	.875
PD9	120	1	5	3.81	1.063
PD10	120	1	5	3.97	.961
Valid N (Likewise)	120				

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 17, it is apparent that the lowest mean score has been found on the statement PD9 (3.81) namely: "I purchase the ready-to-drink tea products on a regular basis." The implication of this finding is that the consumers do not regularly purchase the products of Ichi Ocha.

Furthermore, the recapitulation on the mean score of Purchase Decision between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 18 below.

Table 18. Recapitulation on the Mean Score of the Purchase Decision between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

No	Statements of Product Quality	Mean Score of Teh Botol Sosro	Mean Score of Ichi Ocha
1	I decide to purchase the ready-to-drink tea product because of my needs.	4.45	4.29
2	I look for some information first prior to purchasing the ready-to-drink tea product.	3.96	3.95
3	I purchase the ready-to-drink tea product because the brand of the product is already well-known.	4.19	4.03
4	I like purchasing the ready-to-drink tea product because of recommendations.	4.18	3.97
5	I choose the ready-to-drink tea product according to the favourable taste.	4.21	4.17
6	I will re-purchase the ready-to-drink tea product.	4.20	4.06
7	I choose the easily affordable ready-to-drink tea product.	4.30	4.09
8	I purchase the ready-to-drink tea because the price is acceptable for me.	4.25	4.12
9	I purchase the ready-to-drink tea product routinely.	3.97	3.81
10	I purchase the ready-to-drink tea product because the package of the product is interesting.	3.97	3.97

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by Microsoft Excel (2019)

From the recapitulation in Table 18 above, it is apparent that there have been differences in the Purchase Decision between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. The most prominent difference is found in the statement PD9. The implication of this finding is that the consumers indeed purchase the ready-to-drink tea products due to their heavy schedules but they prefer Teh Botol Sosro more than Ichi Ocha in terms of regular purchase base.

4.3 Hypothesis Test

After the overall data have gathered by means of the research instrument, the researchers perform the hypothesis test in order to identify the influence of each independent variable toward the objects of the study namely The Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. This test is conducted by using the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. Then, the results of the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Teh Botol Sosro might be consulted in Table 19 below.

Table 19. Results of One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Teh Botol Sosro

		PQ	T	B	PD
N		120	120	120	120
Normal Parameter, B	Mean	4,138	4.112	4.113	4.168
	Std. Deviation	.4399	.4444	.5329	.3744
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.143	.187	.207	.125
	Positive	.126	.100	.151	.061
	Negative	-.143	-.187	-.207	-.125
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.569	2.050	2.273	1.373
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.015	.000	.000	.46

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 19 above, it is apparent that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value for the variable Product Quality (PQ) and Purchase Decision (PD) is 0.15 and 0.046 respectively. Since the value is lower than 0.050, it might be stated that the data have not been normally distributed. On the contrary, Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value for the variable Taste (T) and Brand (B) is 0.000 and 0.000 respectively. Therefore, it might also be stated that the data have not been normally distributed.

Then, the results of the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 20 below.

Table 20. Results of One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Ichi Ocha

		PQ	T	B	PD
N		120	120	120	120
Normal Parameter, B	Mean	4.038	4.150	4.069	4.046
	Std. Deviation	.5265	.4356	.6076	.4761
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.146	.187	.180	.152
	Positive	.079	.096	.102	.076
	Negative	-.146	-.187	-.180	-.152
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.595	2.052	1.968	1.665
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.012	.000	.001	.008

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 20 above, it is apparent that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value for the variable Product Quality (PQ) and Purchase Decision (PD) is 0.012 and 0.008 respectively. Since the value is lower than 0.050, it might be stated that the data have not been normally distributed. On the contrary, Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value for the variable Taste (T) and Brand (B) is 0.000 and 0.001 respectively. Therefore, it might also be stated that the data have not been normally distributed.

In order to differentiate the mean score between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of all independent variables, the researchers should perform another One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. The results of this test might be consulted in Table 21 below.

Table 21. Results of the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Differentiating the Mean Score Between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

		Teh Botol Sosro	Ichi Ocha
N		120	120
Normal Parameter, B	Mean	108.78	106.53
	Std. Deviation	7.911	9.665
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.111	.112
	Positive	.083	.05
	Negative	-.111	-.112
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.218	1.230
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.103	.097

a. Test distribution is Normal.
b. Calculated from data.

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 21 above, it is apparent that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value for Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is 0.103 and 0.097 respectively. Since both values have been higher than 0.05, then it might be confirmed that the data for both brands have been normally distributed.

4.4 Discussions

In this section, the researchers would like to elaborate more on the findings that have been gathered from the hypothesis test. The discussions will entail the four independent variables with the results of the Mann-Whitney Mean Differential Test as the basis. Mann-Whitney Mean Differential Test, or also known as Mann-Whitney Test, is a non-parametric test that has been implemented in order to identify the differences in the median between two independent groups if the data of the dependent variable are ordinal or interval/ratio but is not normally distributed. This model has been used in order to test two independent variables or more that have been taken from the same population.

Then, the results of the Mann-Whitney Test for Product Quality of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 22 below.

Table 22. Results of the Mann-Whitney Test for Product Quality between The Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

Ranks				
	Product Name	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank
Product Quality	The Botol Sosro	120	126.08	15129.50
	Ichi Ocha	120	114.92	13790.50
	Total	240		

Test Statistics	
Mann-Whitney U	6530.500
Wilcoxon W	13790.500
Z	-1.259
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.208

a. Grouping Variable: Product Name

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

In relation to the Mann-Whitney Test, the null hypothesis (Ho) for Product Quality is that the Product Quality between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is similar while the alternative hypothesis (Ha) for Product Quality is that the Product Quality between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is different. From the results in Table 22, it is apparent that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.208, which has been higher than 0.050 ($0.208 > 0.050$). Therefore, it might be concluded that the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted or, in other words, the Product Quality between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is similar.

Next, the results of the Mann-Whitney Test for Taste of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 23 below.

Table 23. Results of the Mann-Whitney Test for Taste between The Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

Ranks				
	Product Name	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank
Taste	The Botol Sosro	120	117.45	14094.00
	Ichi Ocha	120	123.55	14826.00
	Total	240		

Test Statistics	
Mann-Whitney U	6834.000
Wilcoxon W	14094.000
Z	-.691
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.490

a. Grouping Variable: Product Name

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

In relation to the Mann-Whitney Test, the null hypothesis (Ho) for Taste is that the Taste between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is similar while the alternative hypothesis (Ha) for Taste is that the Taste between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is different. From the results in Table 23, it is apparent that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.490, which has been higher than 0.050 ($0.490 > 0.050$). Therefore, it might be concluded that the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted or, in other words, the Taste between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is similar.

Furthermore, the results of the Mann-Whitney Test for Brand of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 24 below.

Table 24. Results of the Mann-Whitney Test for Brand between The Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

Ranks				
	Product Name	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank
Brand	The Botol Sosro	120	121.13	14538.50
	Ichi Ocha	120	119.85	14381.50
	Total	240		

Test Statistics	
Mann-Whitney U	7121.500
Wilcoxon W	14381.500
Z	-.149
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.881

a. Grouping Variable: Product Name

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

In relation to the Mann-Whitney Test, the null hypothesis (Ho) for Brand is that the Brand between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is similar while the alternative hypothesis (Ha) for Brand is that the Brand between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is different. From the results in Table 24, it is apparent that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.881, which has been higher than 0.050 ($0.881 > 0.050$). Therefore, it might be concluded that the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted or, in other words, the Brand between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is similar.

Last but not least, the results of the Mann-Whitney Test for Purchase Decision of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha might be consulted in Table 25 below.

Table 25. Results of the Mann-Whitney Test for Purchase Decision between The Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

Ranks				
	Product Name	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank
Purchase Decision	The Botol Sosro	120	129.07	15488.50
	Ichi Ocha	120	111.93	13431.50
	Total	2140		

Test Statistics	
Mann-Whitney U	6171.500
Wilcoxon W	13431.500
Z	-1.920
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.055
a. Grouping Variable: Product Name	

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

In relation to the Mann-Whitney Test, the null hypothesis (Ho) for Purchase Decision is that the Purchase Decision between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is similar while the alternative hypothesis (Ha) for Purchase Decision is that the Purchase Decision between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is different. From the results in Table 25, it is apparent that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.055, which has been higher than 0.050 ($0.055 > 0.050$). Therefore, it might be concluded that the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted or, in other words, the Purchase Decision between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is similar.

In order to identify the total number of respondents who consume both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha, the researchers perform the Overall One-Sample t-test. The results of the One-Sample t-test might be consulted in Table 26 below.

Table 26. Results of the Overall One-Sample t-test for Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha

One-Sample Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Teh Botol Sosro	120	108.78	7.911	.722
Ichi Ocha	120	106.53	9.665	.882

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 26 above, it is found that the total number of respondents that have consumed either Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in the study is 120 respondents. Specifically, the mean score of Teh Botol Sosro is 108.775 while the mean score of Ichi Ocha is 106.525.

For confirming the fifth hypothesis, the researchers should perform another One-Sample t-test. The results of the One-Sample t-test for confirming the fifth hypothesis might be consulted in Table 27 below.

Table 27. Results of One-Sample t-test for Confirming the Fifth Hypothesis

One-Sample Test					
Test Value = 104					
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
				Lower	Upper
The Botol Sosro	6.612	119	.000	3.35	6.20
Ichi Ocha	2.862	119	.000	.78	4.27

Source: Results of Data Processing Activities by SPSS 23

From the results in Table 27 above, it is clear that the t-count value of Teh Botol Sosro is 6.612 while the t-count value of Ichi Ocha is 2.812. Then, the Sig. (2-tailed) value or the significance value with two samples for both products is 0.000 and 0.005 respectively. With the null hypothesis (Ho) that the mean score of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is not equal to 104 (80% from the ideal mean score) and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) that the mean score of both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is equal to 104 (80% from the ideal mean score), it might be concluded that the alternative hypothesis is accepted ($0.000 < 0.050$ and $0.005 < 0.050$). In other words, it might be stated that the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted or the mean score of Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha has been higher than the ideal mean score, namely 80% or 104. Thus, it might be safely stated that both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha have been able to satisfy the consumers' needs.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In this section, the researchers would like to propose the conclusions and the suggestions and also the implications for future researchers. These aspects might be consulted in the following sections.

5.1 Conclusions

Departing from the results that have been found and the discussions within the study, the researchers would like to draw several conclusions. These conclusions are related to the comparison between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of Product Quality, Taste, Brand and Purchase Decision. Then, the conclusions are as follows:

- a. Based on the comparative analysis, there is not any significant difference between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of Product Quality.

- b. Based on the comparative analysis, there is not any significant difference between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of Taste.
- c. Based on the comparative analysis, there is not any significant difference between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of Brand.
- d. Based on the comparative analysis, there is not any significant difference between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of Purchase Decision.
- e. Based on the comparative analysis, there is not any significant difference between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha in terms of Ideal Mean Score Achievement since the mean score of both brands has been higher than 80%.

In addition, although there is not any significant difference between the two brands, the market share between Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha is different and the difference is found in the product branding, the package branding and the taste, resulting in the different purchase decision among the consumers. According to the Theory of Communicative Action, the factor that influences the purchase decision is a similar agreement among the consumers of Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha with regards to the taste. As a result, the products from both brands are enjoyed by the consumers especially in Indonesia.

5.2 Suggestions

Departing from the above conclusions, the researchers would like to provide suggestions with regards to the Product Quality, Taste, Brand and Purchase Decision for both Teh Botol Sosro and Ichi Ocha. For Teh Botol Sosro, although this brand has been in the market competition for a long time, the researchers still find several setbacks. In order to improve the brand, the researchers would like to propose the following suggestions for Teh Botol Sosro:

- a. In order to improve the Product Quality, Teh Botol Sosro should pay more attention to the product so that the product that has been sold to the consumers will not be easily damaged or flawed.
- b. In order to improve the Taste, Teh Botol Sosro should pay more attention to the level of sweetness/bitterness of the tea so that the consumers might consume the product of Teh Botol Sosro with the right taste.
- c. In order to improve the Brand, Teh Botol Sosro that has long been well-known among the consumers should have a higher mean score in comparison to the competitors. By doing so, it is possible that Teh Botol Sosro is able to maintain the brand so that the brand will gain a competitive edge in comparison to the competitor.
- d. In order to improve the Purchase Decision, Teh Botol Sosro should pay more attention to the price of the product so that the product might be afforded by the people from the lower class-economy.

On the other hand, for Ichi Ocha is a new brand that has been able to provide the ready-to-drink green tea with premium quality among the consumers through the combination between the best Japanese green tea and the perfect brewery innovation, the researchers still would like to propose several suggestions so that Ichi Ocha might increase the number of market segment. Then, in order to improve the brands, the researchers would like to propose the following suggestions for Ichi Ocha:

- a. In order to improve Product Quality, Ichi Ocha should pay more attention to the product so that the product will be more interesting than the competitor's product.
- b. In order to improve the Taste, Ichi Ocha should pay more attention to the taste composition so that the product might be enjoyably consumed by the consumers.
- c. In order to improve the Brand, Ichi Ocha might fund several events such as festivals. By doing so, Ichi Ocha, which has been launched by Indofood Asahi, will be considered as the product that is well-qualified since it is able to meet the needs and the desires of the wide consumers.
- d. In order to improve the Purchase Decision, Ichi Ocha should pay more attention to the price of the product so that the product will be competitive with the product of the competitor.

Last but not least, for the researchers who would like to pursue a similar topic in the future, it is suggested that the other variables that might influence the Purchase Decision should be added. At the same time, it is also suggested that future researchers improve the instrument by adding the number of statements in the indicators and also the number of variables. Finally, it is suggested that the future researchers analyse first the characteristics of both the subjects and the objects so that they will attain more specific results.

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